

NOVEMBER RAIN: THE SONG THAT EVOLVED FROM EPIC TO PHENOMENON

 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8211684

Sérgio Rodrigues de Souza

Philosopher. Psychoanalyst. Postdoctoral in Psychology. Email:

srgrodriguesdesouza@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This essay addresses the theme of one of the most iconic songs in the history of international music: November Rain, written by the Californian hardcore band Guns N' Roses, present on the album Use Your Illusion I, released in 1991. work is an analysis of how the song goes from classic to epic, in an infinitely short space of time, disregarding all the time it spent being designed and arranged, within the musical scope planned by the band's musicians, in particular, their vocalist, Axl Rose. The year after its release, the music video for the song is released, becoming a resounding success, through a surreal and unimaginable production, in the music industry, until then. The methodology used was that of hermeneutic analysis, based on interviews published by members of the band about the story of that song and, in the reading of the short story Without You, by Del James, which has an introduction by Axl Rose and which, through this introductory text, much is clarified about the final production of the song and its subsequent insertion in the short film based on the story, which makes it rise to stardom and become a musical phenomenon. November Rain is a song that has lyrics that are very typical of someone alienated in their own world, expressed in the form of an existential, gothic poem, where the composer presents a very intense conflict situation, caused by the excessive care of his partner; but, that due to his unstable psychological state and, bordering on insanity, he interprets it as a nervous tension, something as if he felt suffocated, not by her love, but by her excessive protection; however, his unconscious interprets these confused feelings as a form of survival, understanding that, if left to himself, he would succumb to the madness that his existence represents.

Keywords: November Rain. Axl Rose. Armas e Rosas. Without You.

INTRODUCTION

November Rain is a classic and epic song, composed and performed by a Californian hardrock group, Guns N' Roses, which entered the ultra select list of songs that became immortalized, in itself, given the quality of its composition and production. and, also, for the publicity work of the group itself, in its shows and, finally, for the acclaim of the public, after

a monumental judgment, in several senses. It's much more than a romantic rock song, a ballad; It is a phenomenon that has rarely happened throughout the history of music.

To the same extent, throughout human history, very rare were the musicians who created songs that became classics and, rarer still, are those who produced musical works that became historic and, in the same proportion, with a smaller number found are those who his songs became epics, highlighting only the song by Giuseppe Tartini (1692-1760), *The Trail of the Devil*, composed in 1713.

At the end of the 20th century, the world saw the appearance of a song that went from classic to epic, becoming a phenomenon, that is, the more time passes for it, the more it is adopted and represented in various media and formats. This is the song *November Rain*, lyrical composition that is part of the album *Use Your Illusion I*, by the Californian rock band Guns N' Roses, released in September 1991, by Geffen Records.

The song began to be composed by the band's lead singer, Axl Rose, in 1983, when he was only 21 years old and, until its release, in 1991, his musical maturity was what gave it the shine it deserved. and made her become a phenomenon; something unparalleled in the history of international music, without any legend or supernatural influence in its technical composition; original product of the purest creativity of a musician of rare genius in the subject.

Over the time it was being structured, it went through several versions, including one in which the guitarist of the band Nazareth, Manny Charlton (1941-2022), plays in a version of *November Rain*, of approximately 20 (twenty) minutes. A demo version of the song, created in 1986, presents it in acoustic style, on the piano. Finally, in 1991, it was produced by Mike Clink, lasting almost 9 (nine) minutes and, in addition to the piano solos, 3 (three) metallic guitar solos were inserted, created by Slash, which became iconic and which, due to their unique characteristics, gave music a *sui generis identity*.

November Rain, if composed at a time that allowed for all the erotic mysticism of the Ancient Age that prevailed until the Modern Age, would not lack mystical stories about its inspiration and creation, subliminal messages and other nonsense. However, as it emerged in an environment where this type of feeling no longer applies, or even though creative expressions can be very well explained through psychological theories, its production is the result of long years of hard work with a determined objective, although it has received influences from great artists regarding the style of the instruments to be applied and elaborated. If composed in the period of Classic Antiquity, it would be a divine revelation, manifested through dreams; if produced in the Greco-Hellenic period, it would be a revelation of Apollo, the god of harmonic beauty and music, with a hint of influence from Dionysus, the drunken

god, responsible for human *excesses* . On the contrary, if elaborated in the Middle Ages, it would be a revelation of the Devil, a satire of *shayāṭīn* against humans, defenseless and infidels.

But, as it was composed in an environment in which man became, *ipsis litteris* , the measure of all things and, with this, creativity starts to be understood as the empirical demonstration of the ability to mobilize knowledge in order to If it produces pieces that are capable of enchanting for their aesthetic value, this song, in particular, reveals all the overcoming capacity of an artist and a group with an unparalleled talent for music.

One of the things that makes *November Rain* a song treated in a very sober way, by everyone (without any distinction) is the enmity that Axl created with the North American press and that became an international epidemic. In a recent interview, he claims that it was his naivety, for not knowing the political game of the record companies with the press that led him to treat her with such animosity, causing her to label the band Guns N´ Roses as the most dangerous band on the planet . .

If this was a double game, in which Axl created a minefield with the press so that he was always stamped on the front pages, along with his band and she, in turn, started to detonate them, with the purpose of selling news, what is a fact is that the formula worked perfectly, because the relationship between both became love and hate, in which all the effort of the 5 (five) *badboys* led them to mega stardom, becoming one of the bands most influential in the entire history of universal music, receiving countless awards and resounding success around the planet.

As already stated, the song *November Rain* , the target object of this essay, does not find any support in mystical ideas and other supernatural adventures that could explain it and its enigmatic success that, we take the liberty of referring to it here as a phenomenon . When, in 1992, the video clip of the song was released, it immediately became a *rock opera*, accumulating a range of national and international awards and a success never seen in history .

THE NOVEMBER RAIN SONG

A song is a musical composition in which a series of instruments are mixed, over which the singer's voice is superimposed, where he expresses the lyrics of a poem, with a particular purpose for that group. Each song composed brings a particular story, which the artists try to bring to life through their instruments and voices. According to the musical style of each artist (which can be a group, a duo or a solo singer), the instruments can be varied; but, in the specific

case of rock, usually, these are guitars, bass and vocals; in some cases, including using keyboards.

November Rain is a song that has very typical lyrics of someone alienated in their own world, expressed in the form of an existential, gothic poem, where the composer presents a very intense conflict situation, caused by the excessive care of his partner; but that, due to his psychological state, he interprets it as a nervous tension, something as if he felt suffocated, not by her love, but by her excessive protection; however, his unconscious interprets these confused feelings as a form of survival, understanding that, if left to himself, he would succumb to the madness that his existence represents.

According to Axl, this is a song about not wanting to be in shock and dealing with unrequited love. However, it's hard to say who didn't return whose love; if he was the one who wasn't returning Erin Everly's love, or if it was she who wasn't, in relation to the singer. Axl Rose had become a ticking time bomb, exploding all the time and putting himself in extreme danger. The young man's explosive and uncertain behavior made all those around him pay close attention and, even taking care that, in one of his crises, he did not seriously injure himself, as had happened in certain situations.

What is a fact is that the lyrics ended up being very well constructed and its final chorus reveals an attack of hysteria, in which the individual, with nowhere to run, explodes against someone, who can even be against himself, in a state authoritative denial of help. This behavior reveals a depressive state, in which all help offered is understood as an invasion of a sacred space. The darkness he alludes to in the lyrics is about his depressive state, aggravated by the exhausting pressure of having to continue his band's project, which was beginning to open up in the world of music and the music industry, attracting more and more fans.

In the psychological conditions in which he found himself, it was natural for his friends to try to distance themselves from Axl. His emotional outbursts and his intermittent instability of mood, increasingly volatile, combined with the pressure of producing the new record, in which he, personally (more than any other member of the band), sought to make this new work something that exceeds everything that had already been produced in terms of music in the history of mankind, and it was exactly this expectation that made Steven Adler (the band's original drummer) be thrown out of the group and shortly afterwards it was his turn to Izzy Stradlin (the band's original rhythm guitarist) left the group. Axl declared that he wanted to create and produce something that would surpass the album *Appetite for Destruction*, the band's debut album; but this was a way of justifying all his effort and dedication, and also to mask his real intention, which was too daring.

Specifically, regarding *November Rain*, during the production of the material that gave rise to the albums *Use Your Illusion I and II*, the pressure on all members of the band and the production team was so intense and exhausting that Axl said in the studio that, “if if this song doesn't record well, I'll kill myself; if it is not a success, I leave the career”. It might even seem like an exaggeration; but all of this demonstrates the singer's degree of personal involvement in the production of that song and the requirement for the entire team to be involved in the process.

It seems like a charm, because everyone responded to Axl Rose's effort, motivation, enthusiasm and demands and the music was very well produced, with an unparalleled instrumental sequence. On the other hand, the public consecrated her as a musical phenomenon, taking her to the top of the charts for entire decades, in different countries. Radios around the world declared that they would play the song for life!

Axl referred to her, during the production, which was his *Layla style song*, making an allusion to the classic by the musician Eric Clapton, released in 1970, which has a not so Shakespearean story, but quite complex and with the character getting out of balance from the same way as that of the Persian tale that inspired it. The song *Layla*, one of the great hits of Eric Clapton and the band Derek and The Dominos, is about unrequited love; however, the story behind it reveals much more detail. The song was written for Pattie Boyd, wife of Beatles guitarist George Harrison. George and Pattie were almost Eric's neighbors, in a London suburb of luxury homes, and the musicians ended up developing a friendship in the music business, which meant that they were constantly at each other's houses.

Clapton's proximity to the couple ended up generating a platonic passion with Pattie, which manifested itself in a love letter in the spring of 1970, but it did not have much effect and only left the climate between the two awkward. With that, the skilled guitarist ended up going to Miami, in order to record with the band Derek and The Dominos the album *Layla and Other Assorted Love Songs*, of the same year, in which one of the tracks is the aforementioned song. When Eric showed the lyrics to his friend's beloved wife, he was surprised by a reaction of shame and rejection, which was the final straw for the musician to enter a spiral of heroin addiction for years to come. After recovering from addiction, he went back to looking for Pattie, after all his desire for her never disappeared. With her marriage already collapsed, George wasn't even saddened to see his wife leave with his best friend, even playing at their wedding in 1979.

The name chosen by Clapton to represent Pattie actually comes from an ancient Persian poem entitled *Layla and Majnun*, written in the year 1188, by the poet Nizami Ganjavi. The work tells the story of an impossible love between a princess and a commoner, who ends up

going crazy because he cannot be with his beloved. Changing Pattie's name to Layla not only kept their love in disguise, but also reflected all of Eric's feelings for her and even his delinquent behavior, caused by the loving rejection he had suffered.⁹

The poem that composes the song November Rain was inspired by his own situation of affective conflict that he was going through; however, the entire plot that shaped the videoclip is inspired by the short story *Without You*, from the book *The Language of Fear* (published, in 1995), written by Del James, friend of Axl Rose and former *road manager* of Guns N' Roses. The aforementioned story tells the life story of a singer named Mayne, lead singer of the band *Suicide Shift*. The artist is rich and famous, but with several problems related to drug addiction. He loves his girlfriend, Elizabeth, but cheats on his partner. He tries to arrange a meeting with her near a place where he was going to play. The young woman makes up an excuse saying she couldn't go; but, in fact, she was preparing a surprise for him. Upset, Mayne decides to enjoy the night with other women. At the hotel where the band were staying and Elizabeth arrives just in time. Devastated, the young woman runs away, disappears for a few days. At one point, Mayne releases a song called *Without You*, which is dedicated to Elizabeth. The two broke up some time later. When the singer goes to the woman's house to try to reconcile, he hears the sound of a shot and discovers that she committed suicide.

Here is a passage from the short story in which Del James narrates Elizabeth's suicide:

“When he reached her floor with the elevator, he heard familiar music. As he got closer to her apartment, the volume increased. Then, her world began to spin uncontrollably as a gunshot echoed through the hallway. He ran through her apartment, humiliated, shoulders slumped, careless abandon pounding on the wooden door. He found Elisabeth on the sofa, bleeding profusely, most of her head splattered on the wall behind her. On the coffee table in front of her, spattered with blood, was a ballpoint pen and many balls of crumpled paper with things written on it. He was destroyed before her body. How could this have happened? All he ever did was love her. Devastated, he walked slowly over to the stereo. A CD with the single *Without you* was scheduled for repeat. He tried to imagine how many times she had heard that

⁹The song *Layla* was inspired by the tale of a 12th century Persian writer, Nizami Ganjavi, who would go on to become the most celebrated poet of epic romances in Persian literature, to this day. One of Nizami's most famous poems is the tale of *Layli the Majnun* (773 AH), which in turn was adapted from an even older Arabic tale. In the tale, the young Majnun falls madly in love with Layli, but the young woman's father prevents them from meeting. Majnun will spend all his days writing poems for Layli and singing them in public, but nothing can stop the girl's father from forcing her to marry another man. Majnun goes crazy and starts to inhabit the desert, walking naked, like another wild beast. Layli preserves her virginity, resisting her husband's advances until he dies. The young people can finally be together, but Layli finds out about Majnun's dementia and dies of heartbreak. Eventually, Majnun searches for his beloved and discovers the tomb. Majnun dies there and the young are buried together...

song and turned the sound off. Then he noticed that next to the answering machine was a letter. *Number one with a bullet*, was written on the red-splattered letter” (DEL JAMES, 1993, p. 15).

The scene in question is very Hamletian, with a strong presence of Greek tragic drama in the style of Euripides, in which the death of the protagonist makes the main character live under the weight of guilt for having despised her. The most interesting thing about this contemporary drama is that the tale was inspired by the life of Axl Rose and the troubled relationship between him and his girlfriend at the time, Erin Everly. Could it be that the author thought that the singer would not perceive the direct relationship between the life he lived and the one that the fictional character led? A striking fact is that, 7 (seven) years after the story was written, the vocalist writes a preface and only 2 (two) years after that it is published and, in 1986, at the same time that the story was produced, the songs *Don't Cry* and *November Rain* also came to life, the first being responsible for the contract with Geffen Records, that same year. Thus, Del James' tale may have greatly influenced the production of the epic symphonic ballad and, not necessarily, the production of the lyrics, which can be confirmed by the words expressed by Axl himself, in the preface of the work described:

“For me, the short story *Without You* helped me focus on what could happen in my life, and often what did. Although Del was inspired by situations I was going through at the time, this was his way of helping me to admit and face a painful situation. This, perhaps, has prevented me from going too far a few times. When people are looking for their own identity and things are not going well, they will know if they are bad and losers, and based on that, they create an identity. [...] For years, I've been thinking about making this book or a feature film based on *Without you*, and it kept me centered on not wanting to become Mayne even though he was basically me” (AXL ROSE, 1993, p. 9).

Without you is the typical Gothic text, too heavy for the author to have the courage to release it before being duly submitted to the judgment of those who have the power and courage to judge it. When he read it, still in 1986, when they barely had an initial contract signed with a major label, but knowing that they would have to overcome countless barriers to stardom, Axl saw himself as the main character, committing all the excesses that fame and desire allowed. Instead of getting angry with the author, he took it as a premonition, what fate had in store for him in the not-so-distant future, in case he didn't understand the limits that life places, even for someone who is living far beyond the limit and what is reasonable. . This perception of his is very clear in the *November Rain* videoclip.

The fact that the short story was released in 1995 could be a *marketing ploy*, thought up by Axl himself, in which, with this, he would give a real meaning and, at the same time,

abstract, to the production of music, with a background story to guide her. A work of art, by itself, is not able to enchant anyone, not even its creator, if it is not supported by a creation myth. Del James' work was a gift from the gods to the singer, allowing him to produce a classic that went from epic to phenomenon, without anyone realizing what was happening, why and how. The day would come when everyone, without exception, would charge the band with the inspiration for that musical phenomenon that had been transformed into a rock opera by the creativity of a group of hairy, emotionally unstable hoodlums. At least that was what the press tried to show at all times; which could have been another smokescreen to cover up their creative ventures of high musical *performance*, because fans of all ages and other rock groups did not fail to admire the work of the members and to be enchanted with the songs released by them.

So far, the issue of the poetry that composes the song and its literary and historical influences has been addressed. From now on, this topic will deal with the orchestration of the music, the sonority and its entire stylistic plot, which proves to be a delicate situation, because in its production the song November Rain became a space where it was proved *that* every type of instrument was able to gain more brightness and power to the song. Axl Rose stated in 1993 about creating the song that, "What was really amazing about it was being overwhelmed by the sounds and working with all these new sounds. I mean, I'm in a rock band that you just work with mostly guitars, drums, vocals and bass. But working with strings, flugelhorn and certain bells was almost like magic."

The music, mounted on a classical piano sound, flute, with striking sounds of drums and bass to guide the whole course and an orchestra in the background that, at the time of the recording of the albums, were arrangements elaborated from synthesizers; but, the fact is that no one belittled her and her magical production, for a tiny detail. Although there is someone who says that it was composed exclusively by Axl and, credit was given to the other members of the band, this is a fallacy, because the biggest and best musicians in the world of hardcore music were gathered in the same place at that moment. , all with experience in various instruments and, because of this, knew their limits and also what they would be able to provide, with the necessary freedom to dare to go beyond.

The three metallic solos Slash deploys in the song are far beyond a peerless master's work; it would be more interesting to consider it as a gift offered to a great friend, whom one has in the condition of a brother; because, they are not only beautiful; they are singular. They can even reproduce them with maximum fidelity; but, no other musician will ever be able to create something so brilliant, so deep and so full of feeling. Musician Slash bested Musician

Slash on that production, making it something worthy of the gods; which is to say that, with this, it deserves the title of *epic* .

The song became a strong presence in the band's presentations, since its release. One show, in particular, that became remarkable and emblematic for Axl was what they did in Bogotá, capital of Colombia (South America), on November 30, 1992. During the show, it started to rain and the rain fell inside the stage and this occurred during the execution of the song *November Rain* . Axl declared that this was a special moment for him, because *November Rain* had been at the top of the songs, (No. 1) in Colombia for 60 (sixty) weeks on end, the equivalent of 1 (one) year and two months.

On January 22, 2023, Axl played an emotional version of *November Rain* , on the piano, at the memorial for Lisa Marie Presley, daughter of superstar Elvis Presley. She had died on January 12 of the same year. Lisa was a close friend, very dear to the vocalist and her death left him very shaken. In his obituary, the charge of feeling is so deep and intense that it sounds as if he is standing in front of the Muse, telling him that, don't worry, because we are all fine... And then, a song with an epic story plays, in which he portrays the existential conflict of a classic character.

November Rain is the typical song that came to life beyond its creator. Nothing that can be written about her will prove and even show itself as being enough to clarify her uniqueness in the field of universal music. Axl surpassed all the other musicians who influenced him in the composition of this song and, by overcoming, let it be understood, he went further in art, technique and dived so deeply that only the song itself was able to bring him back to the real world; perhaps he did so so that he himself could admire the greatness, magic and uniqueness of what he built.

Although the song *November Rain* was officially released only on the third studio album by Guns N 'Roses, in 1991, the track is dated from the early 1980s. Colleagues of Axl Rose even revealed that they witnessed the *frontman* playing different versions of the song circa 1983 (eight years before the official edition was released). According to Tracii Guns, former guitarist and founding member of Guns N' Roses, Axl had been working on this song since 1983.

It's no secret that Axl's dream was to create a song that surpassed *Stairway to Heaven* , by Led Zeppelin, created in 1970 and released in 1971 . to reveal *something that went further*, that dared more in production, with more instruments and voices. The result was something surprising and that exceeded all expectations that could even be imagined in relation to it. The guitar solo in the song exceeds 1 minute in different versions and was listed at number 6 on the list of the *100 Greatest Guitar Solos* , by *Guitar World magazine* , in 2006.

One detail is that all musicians in the band are polysemous and with well-known histories regarding the use of other instruments. It must have been an immeasurable challenge to imagine flutes, piano, banjo, trumpet and an entire orchestra, allied with a choir singing a lyrical melody as if it were a rock song. If it's true that Duff (bassist) and Slash (guitarist) were reluctant to admit to creating something of this level, it's no wonder ; because, at the time of production, it seemed to be something that only the gods could prove capable of creating. And, once ready, how to present it live? And they knew Axl would take her to the shows. What's more, audiences would demand that it be performed live!

On November 11, 2022, the track originally released over 30 years ago underwent a complete makeover thanks to the leader of the Porcupine Tree and production assistant Steven Wilson , who was responsible for mixing, and a 50-piece orchestra conducted and arranged by Emmer Christopher Lennertz , who recorded new parts for the iconic song. This condition shows that even an epic like *November Rain* can be improved upon from an increment that only imparts more weight to the song and a deeper hue.

When talking about the new version of the legendary song, Steven Wilson enthusiastically pointed out: “My mix of a fully orchestrated version of Guns N' Roses' evergreen *November Rain* appears on the 30th anniversary reissue of *Use Your Illusion* . The new version, from 2022, is the same *performance* as the original, and mixed faithfully to the established version, but with newly recorded orchestration, replacing the sampled sounds used at the time.”

One might wonder why they didn't do this already, in 1991, for the first version of the song. That's a difficult answer and, even if they had the money for it, they would have to find an orchestra willing to learn a song they had never heard in their lives, even destroying the element of surprise that the albums promised. The first time the band played unreleased songs from the albums to be released was at the *Rock in Rio II festival* , in Brazil, in January 1991. It can be said that this was the first show on the *Use Your Illusion Tour* , although it was not officially .

This performance, in particular, would already show what to expect from the band, in terms of music and sound, evolving from English punk rock to a more progressive style in the songs; but nobody expected that from a rock group with Guns' history something so surprising could be born. Not that they couldn't; the entire music world realized that there was an unparalleled musician who was capable of enchanting the entire audience with his *performance* on stage and a maestro who was capable of enchanting the entire audience with his guitar. When Slash plays, it's far more than an instrument producing sound; he seems to be merging with his

act of production, in a symbiotic process that is impossible to describe precisely. The freedom with which he explores musical notes and arrangements makes him an incomparable musician and, in *November Rain*, he knew how to leave his mark.

It's no secret to Guns N' Roses fans that the band already had a vast repertoire of compositions before starting to record their first album, *Appetite For Destruction* (1987). Some songs, like *November Rain*, eg, were ready by mid-1986; however, they were only used in the later *Use Your Illusion I and II*, both released simultaneously in September 1991.

This question about the choice of songs to compose the band's first studio album and the decision to leave some other songs out of it is not difficult to explain. The 1980s experienced, in hardcore music, an experience that came from the *New Wave of British Heavy Metal*¹⁰ and, although the intention was to overcome Punk Rock, heavy music absorbed much of this movement, which also appeared in England itself, the land of that gave birth to Heavy Metal. There was no room, at that exact moment, for romantic songs with a multi-instrumental style, which would soften it, as was the band's proposal in the composition of *November Rain*.

The decision about which songs to leave out of the *Appetite for Destruction* album was very technical and based on a great knowledge of the phonographic and musical market at that moment that international rock was experiencing. Thus, the band exaggerated with more serious guitar and bass riffs, with punk rock drums and an aggressive vocal: just the right measure to please everyone and the recipe was phenomenal, because combined with lyrics that brought from the streets and nightclubs of Los Angeles the whole naked reality of existence, the result was what the band became from 1991 onwards: a true musical phenomenon!

Why was *November Rain* in particular off the *Appetite For Destruction* album? Steve Thompson, responsible for mixing the album, revealed the reason why the song was left out at the time, in an interview given to Mitch Lafon, in 2022: "I loved the song, but I thought the direction of the album was more 'punk rock in the face'. And I felt that *November Rain* didn't

¹⁰*New Wave of British Heavy Metal (NWOBHM)* – (*New Wave of British Heavy Metal*) was a musical movement from England, which emerged between the 1970s and 1980s. Despite the name, it spread across Europe and the world. With *new wave* and *disco music* comes a unique movement of bands that seek to rescue heavy metal, including the particularities of the style. *The New Wave of British Heavy Metal* re-energized heavy metal in the late 1970's and early 1980's. By the late 1970's heavy metal was stagnating with its biggest stars (Led Zeppelin and Black Sabbath) seeking new directions that fled from their metallic roots, such bands lost themselves in their own indulgences, making room for the emerging punk rock that seemed to meet the needs of a proletarian, unemployed and hopeless English youth. The *New Wave of British Heavy Metal* took the blues of the first generation of metal, adding weight and speed to the same highlighting the metallic aspects of that style. Without worrying about reaching large audiences and reaching them however, it was pure fan metal. Perhaps this is the reason why so-called traditional metal is largely modeled after *New Wave bands of British Heavy Metal*. **Source:** <https://www.masterclass.com/articles/new-wave-of-british-heavy-metal>, 2021.

fit. Great song, had great potential. Obviously, when he came out on *Use Your Illusion I*, Axl did what he needed to do to complete his vision on that path.”

Regarding the song *November Rain* not being included in the repertoire of the first album, the explanation is not as simple as one might assume, going far beyond a marketing strategy and knowledge of the music market. What has been said above about the *New Wave of British Heavy Metal* helps to clarify part of the situation; but it stays on the surface. Thompson realized that there was something extraordinary in that song and that it needed another type of intervention, such as financial resources. With the budget available at the time, it would fall short of what it could become, frustrating everyone and also depriving humanity of the opportunity for extraordinary classical music.

But what weighs heavily on this decision is that *November Rain* was born to be composed and performed by *titans* ! And, who was Axl Rose, Slash and company at that time? None other than members of a hardcore band, living in the suburbs of Los Angeles and getting into trouble with the police, and with the fans, at every performance. But, in 1991, exactly after the band's apothecic performance at the Rock in Rio festival, in January of that same year, the band returned to their homeland as a star on the rise: the magical moment had arrived for the release of that song. It would no longer be performed by a group of talented musicians; would be performed by a group of musical giants; someone with the freedom to dare in the world of musical artistic creativity, because he had ascended to a level that only a few reach: mega stardom!

This, however, made the band even more demanding in terms of production. So much so that, as soon as they return to Los Angeles from Brazil, Slash alleges that he did not like the mixes of the songs on the album to be released and, the album that was practically ready, with expectations of release for March 1991, extended until September of the same year.

November Rain is one of those typical creations that have a life of their own even before they come to light; they have a unique psychology that cannot be contradicted; therefore, a whole study on the propitious moment for them to be presented to the general public (the true art critic whose opinion, in fact, interests the artists) must be considered in its entirety. Axl was already a classical pianist and Slash, a guitarist with an unmistakable style, a musician everyone wanted to see and hear play. It was what the song needed to come to life and everything else that composes it was adornment over a musical structure never even thought of in history, since the creation of the piano (1709) and the electric guitar (1947).

The mysticism that can surround it is that it appears, in 1983, at the hands of Axl Rose and from there until it became public, it went through several musical arrangements, as if it

were maturing in silence as the musicians themselves, too, matured in their respective symphonic achievements. By the time it was ready to be presented to a wide audience, its interpreters were already music giants. She wouldn't settle for less!

NOVEMBER RAIN AND THE EVOLUTION FROM ROCK BALLAD TO ROCK OPERA

It is necessary to clarify to the public what a *rock opera* is and what is necessary for a work to be classified as such. Therefore, it is a rock work that presents a narrative told in several parts, songs or sections, in the style of an opera. A rock opera differs from a conventional album in that it usually brings songs unified by a common theme or narrative, telling a story with a beginning, middle and end, which may or may not be presented theatrically. In recorded format, it can be similar to a concept album, although it simply maintains a specific theme or style and the songs are not held together by a plot. It is generally agreed that the main characteristic of an opera shared by rock opera is the consistent narrative, centered on human beings and their conflicts and problems, and that reports these aspects in a cohesive and coherent way. It is a work that expresses a personal drama of none other than Axl Rose himself and his emotional inconstancies.

November Rain turns into a rock opera and an epic from the creation of its videoclip, which is much more than a brilliant work of art; becoming a colossal production with a life of its own. Attentive to a chronological question, the song, as well as the lyrics, could not have been influenced by the story by Del James *Without you*, written at the end of 1986, since, in the middle of that year, the music was already properly composed. But, regarding the music video, the influence of the referred story is clear; the composition strongly fits what Axl wrote in the presentation of the aforementioned short story, published in 1993, regarding his fear of becoming a Mayne, in which life does not just imitate art; but he repeats it literally.

Axl spent 5 (five) years in intensive psychoanalytic therapy, and the influence of this technique on the videoclip is also very expressive, in which everything can be interpreted as a manifest desire. The video starts with him, getting ready to sleep, having to use medication and, it is a stormy night, marked by strong thunder and strong winds that illuminate his room through the window. Then there's a wedding, and at a glance he's deep in a very restless sleep. Everything goes perfectly at the wedding, with an image of Jesus Christ pouring blood from his eyes, as if it all represented a bad omen. Everyone is happy celebrating at a big party, when it starts to rain and despair takes over everyone, as if that represented the end of the world and, in

the sequence, the bride is placed in a coffin, lifeless and with a doubt. unanswered about her death, not knowing if she committed suicide, like Elizabeth, from the short story *Without you*, or if she was killed by her husband. The music video ends with Axl waking up, in a panic, from his bizarre dream.

The adaptation of Del James' short story to the rock opera *November Rain* is a rare expression of human intelligence in the world of music, in which there is no room for any questions about the production. It was nothing but a nightmare! Taking this issue as a *leitmotif* for the contextual analysis, this expresses the pressure that reading the short story (*Without you*) caused on Axl Rose's psychological state. It is noteworthy that the dream is a manifest desire, which reveals that he wanted his fiancée to die at the time; it could be killing himself (or he kept the desire to kill her), so that she would leave him alone; but her reaction in the video shows that it wasn't quite how she felt, seeing her wish come true.

This is one of those phenomenological situations that go beyond all the limits that human knowledge can reach, in which Physis *chooses* someone to be the interpreter of something great and, despite all the mishaps that mark the life and existence of this individual, it is he who will; because that's how it was already defined. *Without you* served him like a mirror; however, not as an instrument that helped him see his past; but, to introduce you to the future. And, it was fearing this future mirrored by Del James' tale that he tried to focus on his band, in the way he could, even though his attitude demonstrated its imminent destruction.

Axl was diagnosed with manic-depressive psychosis while still in his teens and, despite the fact that he was a very talented and promising young man, he managed to escape being admitted to one of the many asylums that serve these purposes. It is noteworthy that, at the age of 18 (eighteen) he left home and went to live on the streets of Los Angeles, which may have been responsible for not ending up in a madhouse.

When he releases the music video for *November Rain*, which, in fact, is an adaptation of his friend's tale, with an epic song by the band as a musical background, his wish comes true and his demons stop haunting him. What happened thereafter, during and after the *Use Your Illusion tour* (1991-1993) was no longer part of Mayne's ghostly influence. The world of music would no longer be the same and Axl's madness, with all the episodes of excesses around the world would be relegated to the pages of history, for those who wish to understand a little more about the man, who was overcome by myth and for your art.

The *November Rain music video* surpassed the 2 (two) billion views mark on YouTube, on February 15, 2023, and became the first video by a rock artist to reach that mark. It was originally released in 1991 and reached the *streaming platform* only in December 2009. On July

17, 2018, it had reached the mark of 1 (one) billion views on the said platform. In 2017 alone, according to Forbes magazine, the *November Rain music video* was viewed an average of 560,000 times a day. Even more than that, the record holder for views of the clip is Brazil, alongside Mexico and Argentina. It is noteworthy that more than 83% of the video's reproductions came from outside the United States. Using the song from the *Use Your Illusion I album*, the video for *November Rain* was released in 1992.

In the nine-minute epic, frontman Axl Rose marries his then-girlfriend, Stephanie Seymour, before the ceremony is cut short by tragedy. In a striking scene, guitarist Slash heads outside a church in the middle of the desert to deliver the song's solo. Directed by Andy Morahan, legend has it that *November Rain* cost over \$1.5 million to make, making it one of the most expensive music videos of all time. To be exact, it is the 13th most expensive music video in music history.

What draws attention is that the videoclip stays for 6 (six) years being very appreciated and, as soon as the band announces its reunion with the classic formation, with Slash and Duff back, along with Axl Rose, the views of the short skyrocket and soon after reaches a historic figure. In a period of 5 (five) years, this record number doubles; which allows deducing that the magic of the band is in the performance of its members that, in a mysterious and magical way, makes the fans identify with their work represented on stage, as if each show were a true rock opera. Of course, the most enchanting moment of the show is when Axl Rose's piano strums the first notes of *November Rain*, followed by Slash's incomparable solos that permeate it, making it a true epic, in which a mini symphony orchestra plays it together with the traditional musicians of the band.

Donald Trump named the *November Rain* video as *the best video of all time*. The praise of the former President of the United States was revealed in the memoir of Sarah Huckabee Sanders, former White House press officer. In the publication, Sanders describes that Trump originally wanted the song to be placed on the soundtrack of his rallies in 2018. When praising the work of Guns N 'Roses, he made her watch the clip in the Oval Office of the White House to prove his point. view, although Sarah didn't disagree. Trump finally got his wish when the song was played at a campaign event in Michigan.

CONCLUSION

November Rain is a song that has aged in a grand way and, although it was born as a dream of overcoming it, it has become an inspiration for many individuals around the Planet, and can be classified as an unparalleled and unsurpassed creation in the history of music. The quality attributed to him by the musicians of the band is something that has never been seen before.

Its history is extensive, as it takes almost a decade to become public, a fact already explained that, in 1986, it was ready; but, by a joint decision between the producer of the band's first album and the musicians, it was put on *hold* until such time as the *Use Your Ullusion I and II albums* were produced, and the production of the song, in particular, received all the attention Axl deemed necessary to make it a classic masterpiece.

It is necessary to clarify the fact that, even if the story *Without You* , by Del James, is linked, in a mysterious way, to the song, its influence is shown in the music video, which is a short film based on this story and in the psychological condition of Axl Rose, which has *November Rain* as background music.

Understanding Axl Rose's thinking, the short film was to be set to music by the song *Estrangend* (1991) and, by decision of Stephanie Seymour, his girlfriend at the time, the decision fell on the first song and the result was the emergence of a musical phenomenon. Something difficult to explain in a simple way, because everything revolves around the insane experiences that affected the band's lead singer and his difficulty in managing a Dionysian existence.

The song, boosted by the videoclip, became what all humans expect, a phenomenon, a gift from the gods to men who allow them to enjoy it at their pleasure and it is this Dionysian mass feeling that makes the band continue to be one of the most heard on the Planet and doing shows around the world on endless tours.

Del James' short story, *Without You* , remained obscure until 1993, when both the song and the video were already recognized successes, both for music and lyrics and also for film production. In 1995, it was published as part of a collection of short stories by the same author, with an introduction by Axl Rose, where he explains the recognition for the creativity of the author, his personal friend, and the gratitude he felt for having shown him the future of his life and his existence, if he didn't recognize the excesses and extravagances that were consuming him in silence.

REFERENCES

BERNHART, Walter. *Word and Music Studies: Essays in Honor of Steven Paul Scher and on Cultural Identity and the Musical Stage* (Word and Music Studies 4). USA: Editions Rodopi BV, 2002.

https://whiplash.net/materias/news_711/348808-gunsnroses.html

JAMES, D. *The Language of Fear*. New York: Del Pubs, 1995.

MOORE, AF *The Beatles: Sgt. Pepper's Lonely Hearts Club Band* (Cambridge Music Handbooks). Cambridge (UK): CambridgeUniversityPress, 1997.

ROSE, WA Introduction. In: JAMES, D. *The Language of Fear*. New York: Del Pubs, 1995, p. 8-10.

WITHOUT, by DEL JAMES. Axl Rose Fan Club. Available at: <http://axlrosefaclub.com/del-james/>. Accessed on May 15, 2023.